

CESSDA Annual Report 2022

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Foreword by the Chair

2022 was another year of major changes. Russia invaded Ukraine on February 24, 2022, targeting Ukraine's critical infrastructure. Meanwhile, the rest of the world struggled to adapt to the shocks and fallouts of the invasion of a neighbour into another European country.

2022 was also the year in which the World Health Organization declared that the end of the pandemic was 'in sight'. Three years after COVID burst onto the scene, many countries abandoned the lockdowns, travel restrictions, and related measures that they had imposed when COVID swept across the world in early 2020.

In the world of research, COVID-19 left behind also a vast quantity of research, data, and collaboration networks. Vaccination and therapeutic treatments were created at an unforeseen speed due to the heavy investment and focus on finding ways to get through the pandemic. In addition to its own wide provision of information on COVID-related data, CESSDA was involved in a large-scale cross-disciplinary effort to offer information on data via a shared portal. The success of this task was aided greatly by the established metadata and vocabulary development within the CESSDA community.

One of the internal changes within CESSDA ERIC was a successful recruitment of a new Director, who joined the organisation to set the strategic direction for a more efficient, inclusive, and member-oriented consortium.

In 2022 my first term ended as the Chair of the General Assembly of CESSDA ERIC. At the meeting in November 2022, I was elected to continue as Chair alongside the Austrian representative Matthias Reiter-Pázmándy, as Vice Chair. Our team will be proud to Chair the GA of CESSDA ERIC for the second two-year term. We are eager to see how CESSDA develops in the coming years. At the same time, we hope that the societal environment will develop into a more peaceful and constructive direction after the turbulence we have seen since 2020.

Helena Laaksonen, Chair of the General Assembly

Foreword by the CESSDA Director

2022 was also a year of change for me. After working for 10 years as Head of Research Affairs at Science Europe, I started my new position in April 2022 at the Main Office of CESSDA ERIC in Bergen. One of my first official representations was attending the final conference of the Social Sciences & Humanities Open Cloud (SSHOC) project as the new Director. SSHOC has been funded by the EU framework programme Horizon 2020 to contribute to the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC). The conference took place in Brussels in early April and left the impression of a reinvigoration of the previous achievements of the project: colleagues, friends, and newcomers finally met face-to-face again after nearly two and a half years after the pandemic swept over the world. That was also when all SSHOC partners signed a Memorandum of Understanding (MoU) to bolster cloud services for the social sciences and humanities.

Another MoU was signed between CESSDA ERIC and OPERAS, the planned research infrastructure for open scholarly communication for social sciences and the humanities, in November 2022.

Between my first Service Provider Forum in May and our General Assembly in May 2023 I met with representatives from all of our 22 Member States. The consultation process for a new strategy cycle for 2023-2027 started in April.

Other outreach activities were the CESSDA-sponsored IASSIST 2022 Conference in Gothenburg, the round table discussions at the ERIC Forum in Brussels and the EDDI 2022 conference in Paris, where I was honoured to give a keynote speech on the European Research Area and the importance of research infrastructures and metadata for cross-disciplinary and international collaboration. These activities contribute to our long-standing objectives around training, mentoring and widening participation.

The maintenance and updates of CESSDA's core technical services are an ongoing priority. At the end of 2022, most Service Providers were successfully onboarded in the CESSDA Data Catalogue (CDC). The interoperability was improved so that metadata from the CDC can be shared easily with external providers such as OpenAIRE, GoTriple and B2Find. Three CESSDA services have successfully been onboarded to the EOSC Portal Catalogue & Marketplace.

In 2022, the Trust Working Group established connections with a network of the Trust community through joint activities such as EOSC Nordic, SSHOC or FAIRsFAIR projects.

Besides external representation, 2022 was also a busy period with proposals submitted on behalf of CESSDA's Service Providers in partnership with valued partners from the five clusters and the 24 ERICs under the umbrella of the ERIC Forum in domains of strategic importance for CESSDA. In 2022, CESSDA ran 10 EC Projects with an estimated budget of eight M. EUR.

In conclusion, CESSDA as a consortium continues to provide collectively excellent research data management solutions for Europe's researchers by providing metadata expertise, developing standards and training to enable interoperability, and making data FAIR.

Bonnie Wolff-Boenisch, CEO

CESSDA 2022 Highlights - European Landscape

Social Sciences and Humanities Open Cluster

In 2022 Europe's open ecosystem for social sciences and humanities (SSH) has reached a key milestone after the core research infrastructures in the Social Sciences Humanities Open Cloud (SSHOC) project signed a Memorandum of Understanding as a commitment to improve access to data, tools, and training for SSH practitioners on 5 April 2022.¹

Composed of European Research Infrastructure Consortia (ERICs), this new entity called the 'SSH Open Cluster' will provide long-term visibility, impact, and sustainability for SSH and its stakeholders by providing high quality 'cloud ready' SSH tools and data throughout Europe.

The SSH Open Cluster will simplify high-level interactions with the EC and other EU bodies enabling effective responses to specific requests for expert advice in the areas covered by the member organisations.

The new SSH Open Cluster will intensify collaboration between different SSH community stakeholders while actively promoting the quality and impact of SSH within the European Research communities and beyond.

The SSH Open Cluster is comprised of European Research Infrastructure Consortia (ERICs) that include: the Consortium of European Social Science Data Archives (CESSDA), Common Language Resources and Technology Infrastructure (CLARIN), Digital Research Infrastructure for the Arts and Humanities (DARIAH), European Social Survey (ESS), and Survey of Health, Ageing and Retirement in Europe (SHARE) as well as emerging research infrastructures such as E-RIHS, EHRI, GGP, GUIDE, OPERAS, RESILIENCE, and other partners such as EVS, WageIndicator, and different universities and institutes.

MoU between CESSDA and OPERAS

CESSDA ERIC signed a Memorandum of Understanding with the OPERAS (Open Scholarly Communication in the European Research Area for Social Sciences and Humanities) to collaborate and share expertise in the area of scholarly communication, services such as the CESSDA Data Catalogue and the GoTriple platform, alignment of policies and practices and training and learning.²

1 <https://sshopencloud.eu/>.

2 OPERAS mission is to coordinate and federate resources to address the scholarly communication needs of European researchers in the field of SSH.

CESSDA and EOSC

CESSDA is very involved in the build-up of the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) a federated, open and multi-disciplinary environment where researchers publish, find, and reuse data, tools and services for research, innovation and educational purposes.

CESSDA is engaged on different levels in EOSC:

- In the EOSC association as a full member.
- In different EOSC task forces through CESSDA Service Providers (SPs).
- In different EOSC related projects through the CESSDA Main Office and CESSDA's SPs.

CESSDA is recognised as an early EOSC adopter.

Three of the CESSDA services have been successfully onboarded to the EOSC Catalogue and Marketplace. These are:

- CDC (<https://marketplace.eosc-portal.eu/services/cessda-data-catalogue>).
- CESSDA ELSST (<https://marketplace.eosc-portal.eu/services/elsst-european-language-social-science-thesaurus>).
- CESSDA DMEG (<https://marketplace.eosc-portal.eu/services/data-management-expert-guide-dmeg>).

CESSDA Governance

The General Assembly of CESSDA met in June, August and November 2022. The CESSDA Service Providers' Forum (SPF), an advisory body to the Director, consisting of representatives of CESSDA national Service Providers met twice in April and October 2022.

The major discussion points in the CESSDA bodies were:

- CESSDA's internal developments and impact (see chapter CESSDA Key Performance Indicators).
- Maintenance of existing infrastructure (see chapter Tools & Services).
- Evaluation of outputs of CESSDA's work plan and in-house funding streams ('Agenda').
- Alignment within the SSH domain and other SSH research infrastructures.
- Alignment with other non-SSH research infrastructures in the context of the cluster work with the other four clusters ENVRI-FAIR, EOSC-Life, ESCAPE and PANOSC.
- Participation in diverse activities and tasks in the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC).
- Starting the consultation process for a new strategy cycle for the period 2023-2027.

CESSDA Key Performance Indicators

In 2022 CESSDA started its second key performance indicator collection. The results of the second CESSDA Key Performance Indicator (C-KPI) collection demonstrate the large diversity of Service Providers in terms of size, capacity and maturity, and the variation of their practices in data collection, interpretation, reporting and presentation.

The constantly changing digital environment requires regular technical updates and upgrades. This introduces changes in data collection methodologies and the repository (architecture).

The variability in responses across Service Providers for KPIs on digital objects comprise different definitions of 'primary digital objects', variations on types of objects within a collection, and variations in change management and versioning approaches. CESSDA will work to improve the specification of these definitions and improve alignment.

CESSDA Policies

CESSDA Data Access Policy

In 2022, the CESSDA Data access policy was updated to reflect the FAIR principles, the EU General Data Protection Regulation, EU's Open Science Policy and CESSDA's own developments, including the growing membership. Also, the CESSDA PID policy was renewed until 2025.³ Both policies have implications for the study level metadata produced by the Service Providers and for the services that use it, such as the CESSDA Data Catalogue.

³ <https://www.cessda.eu/News/CESSDA-Newsitem-nid3142>.

Gender Equality Plan

CESSDA published its first Gender Equality Plan (GEP) in 2022, focusing on the following key priority areas: gender leadership and decision-making, gender in recruitment, retention, and career development, work-life balance, and organisational culture, as well as gender training. Following its publication, the GEP

was endorsed by the Director on November 7, 2022, affirming that CESSDA ERIC is committed to the successful implementation of this plan, as "...equity and diversity are essential components of scientific quality and can be a major resource for scientific excellence". The GEP can be found on the CESSDA website.⁴

"On behalf of CESSDA ERIC, it is with great pleasure that I wish to present the CESSDA ERIC **Gender Equality Plan (GEP)**.

The first CESSDA ERIC GEP provides a framework for actions essential to safeguard and guarantee all employees the same rights and opportunities. It also ensures a fair and unbiased process for everyone in the CESSDA secretariat and its bodies."

Dr Bonnie
Wolf-Boenisch

Find out more: <https://www.cessda.eu/News>

CESSDA Outreach

Researchers and Data Community

IASSIST 2022

The conference theme, "Data by Design: Building a Sustainable Data Culture", emphasises two core principles: design and sustainability and what they mean to data communities and researchers. One key question was how these groups are helping design a culture of practices around data that will persist across organisations and over time.

The conference was co-sponsored by CESSDA ERIC and hosted by its member the Swedish National Data Service (SND).⁵ The national research data repository is governed by a consortium of nine Swedish universities and works with over 30 institutions reaching to a large number of researchers.

Metadata Experts

EDDI 2022

The European DDI⁶ (EDDI) conference is a place where the social science data management community meet, exchange ideas, report progress and build DDI capabilities and capacity across Europe. Going online during the pandemic does seem to have stimulated more interest from new groups. The three recent hybrid

⁴ <https://www.cessda.eu/About/Documents-and-Policies>.

⁵ <https://iassist2022.org/>.

⁶ The Data Documentation Initiative (DDI) is an international standard for describing the data produced by surveys and other observational methods in the social, behavioural, economic, and health sciences. DDI is a free standard that can document and manage different stages in the research data lifecycle, such as conceptualization, collection, processing, distribution, discovery, and archiving.

conferences hosted in Paris from 2020-2022 saw in total 274 new participants and 122 new organisations.⁷ The conference was preceded by the Committee on Data of the International Science Council (CODATA).

The conference was opened by the new CESSDA Director with a keynote entitled “The European Research Area - So Far and Yet So Close”, which drew on the development of a European vision for cooperation and her experiences at both Science Europe and the European Research Infrastructure (ESFRI) to illustrate the way in which the incorporation of infrastructure and collaboration is a critical part of delivering the European Research Area’s policy objectives.

Adoption of DDI-Lifecycle and DDI-Codebook at CESSDA was the spur for a number of presentations on how the many archives are managing to provide content for the CESSDA Data Catalogue, and how CESSDA interacts with other European infrastructures, including ECRIN and EOSC. Other topics covered included demonstrations of various tools that support DDI, for example, Dataverse, Colectica and the World Bank’s NADA software.

EDDI 2023 conference will be hosted by CESSDA SP UL-ADP in Ljubljana, Slovenia.

7 Presentations from the Conference are available from <https://zenodo.org/communities/eddi2022>.

CESSDA Consortium Activities

CESSDA's working groups focused on four key areas:

- Tools & Services.
- Trust & Standards.
- Training & Outreach.
- Widening & Mentoring.

Other activities include special focus topics such as 'Widening of the Perimeter of Data' or 'Journal Outreach'. The working groups followed their roadmaps according to the CESSDA Strategic Plan 2018–2022.

Tools & Services

The Tools Working Group focuses on the user's perspective of researchers and Service Providers. The group monitors the status of CESSDA's services, coordinates and evaluates tasks. Besides, maintenance of the group enhances the available CESSDA services and provides direction to new and future services.

The WG supports CESSDA's overarching goal to provide appropriate tools for Service Providers and researchers to curate, preserve, publish, find, access and reuse research data in a multilingual environment.

Highlights in 2022

CESSDA Integration with EOSC

As part of its involvement in the EOSC-Future project, CESSDA onboarded three of its core services in the EOSC Marketplace (see chapter under European Landscape). CESSDA also made use of the EOSC monitoring service to provide availability and reliability statistics. CESSDA also adopted the EOSC Helpdesk. The advantage is that feedback entered by users through the web form associated with the onboarded services creates a ticket in that helpdesk and sends a notification to the CESSDA Main Office technical team. Another advantage is that it reduces costs to CESSDA replacing the existing 'pay-per-user' helpdesk solution. It also simplifies the task of redirecting tickets to other parts of EOSC, when appropriate

CESSDA Data Catalogue

At the end of 2022, most Service Providers were successfully onboarded in the CESSDA Data Catalogue (CDC). The findability of data was increased by exposing metadata for **machine-harvesting**. Interoperability improvements and the new OAI-PMH endpoint mean that metadata from the CDC can be easily shared with external providers such as OpenAIRE, GoTriple and B2Find.⁸ A search **API** was also developed to allow external agencies to use the search functionality of the CDC and to integrate CDC into their own websites and platforms.⁹

⁸ <https://datacatalogue.cessda.eu/documentation/providing-oai-pmh.html>.

⁹ <https://api.tech.cessda.eu/>.

Metadata in JSON-LD/RDF format was embedded in the CDC so that tools like F-UJI can evaluate the catalogue for FAIRness. Consequently, CESSDA created a bulk **FAIR assessment workflow** using the F-UJI tool to assess the FAIR score of CDC which turned out to be relatively high.¹⁰ Studies from the CESSDA Data Catalogue were included in the **COVID-19 Data Portal** as the first new source coming from the BY-COVID project.¹¹

The CESSDA Data Catalogue had over 42,000 records by the end of 2022, which made it the largest Social Science Data Catalogue in the world. CDC is one of the core technical services that has been onboarded to the EOSC marketplace.¹²

CESSDA Vocabulary Service

The CESSDA Vocabulary Service was further improved in 2022, with new controlled vocabularies, additional languages (**including Japanese**), and work on the Simple Knowledge Organization System RDF Schema (SKOS/RDF) export.

CESSDA European Language Social Science Thesaurus

A new version of the European Language Social Science Thesaurus (ELSST) was released in September 2022. Two new languages, **Hungarian and Icelandic**, were added which brought the total number of languages in ELSST to sixteen. Content development work focused on completing the revision of terms related to **'sexuality'** as well as updating terms relating to **'migration'**. The release also included a number of technical innovations that promoted ELSST's compliance with the FAIR principles. Updating the thesaurus ensures that it **reflects societal changes** and **facilitates access to data resources** across Europe. ELSST is part of the **EOSC marketplace**.¹³

CESSDA Euro Question Bank

The CESSDA Euro Question Bank (EQB) is envisioned as a **cross-national question bank** that will integrate and display metadata from several European archives, mostly CESSDA Service Providers. Work on the EQB continued in 2022 by adding question metadata from the SSHOC project.

CESSDA Dataverse

Several CESSDA Service Providers were using or planning to use Dataverse as their repository platform. In 2022, the Service Providers continued to actively exchange experiences, ideas and solutions about Dataverse in the context of CESSDA. In addition, DANS organised a Dataverse train-the-trainer event as part of the CESSDA Training activities.

10 Shepherdson, John, & Papagiannopoulos, Kostas. (2022, December 1). Bulk FAIR assessment of the CESSDA Data Catalogue using the F-UJI API. EDDI2022: The 14th Annual European DDI User Conference (EDDI2022), Sciences Po, Paris, France. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7405623>.

11 CESSDA metadata in the COVID-19 Data Portal: <https://www.covid19dataportal.org/search/social-sciences?crossReferenc esOption=all&overrideDefaultDomain=true&db=cessda-covid19&size=15>.

12 <https://marketplace.eosc-portal.eu/services/cessda-data-catalogue>.

13 <https://marketplace.eosc-portal.eu/services/elsst-european-language-social-science-thesaurus>.

CESSDA Standards: The Metadata Office

The setting up of **DDI Profiles** created by the **Metadata Office** in 2021 ensures that higher quality metadata enters the CESSDA Data Catalogue.¹⁴ As a result, CESSDA provides **machine-readable** specification and **human-readable** guidance to metadata professionals. The wider adoption of the classification systems ELSST and CESSDA Topic Classification, maintained in the CESSDA Vocabulary Service, form a central aspect of this work.

In 2022, the Metadata Office maintained the CESSDA Metadata Model and the DDI profiles and continued to support Service Providers in their implementation. The CESSDA CTO was a member of the DDI Alliance Scientific Board.

Trust & Landscape

The CESSDA Trust Working Group mission derives from the Service Providers' obligations under Annex II Obligation 7 to "Adhere to the principles of the Open Archival Information System reference model and any agreed CESSDA ERIC requirements for operating trusted repositories".¹⁵

Highlights in 2022

CESSDA has selected the 16 **CoreTrustSeal Trustworthy Digital Repository (TDR)** requirements and more than half of Service Providers are certified. The initial and primary activity of the Trust Group is to support Service Providers, both long-standing and recently joined, in achieving CoreTrustSeal. These activities exist at multiple levels of maturity, some introductory but more generally at the intermediate level of aspiring repositories and now at the expert level for those Service Providers undertaking recertification every three years. Trust support has been reactive as different Service Providers sought support and internal peer review of their CoreTrustSeal applications during the year. Maintenance of this on-demand service in the future is a priority.

Figure 1: Status of Certified CESSDA data archives in 2022.

14 <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4580376>.

15 <https://public.ccsds.org/Pubs/650x0m2.pdf>.

During 2022 internal analysis of the topic areas covered by the CoreTrustSeal Requirements, Annex II obligations and CESSDA Key Performance Indicators (see chapter on CESSDA KPIs) resulted in updated support plans for Service Providers and proposals for broader information collection and analysis. Information was categorised to identify value to CESSDA to deliver trend analysis over time and organise Service Providers by tier (e.g. maturity towards a stated goal).

These internally facing activities have been paralleled by the external trust landscape of trust work and the annual landscape report and internal workshop have been delivered.

More recently internal support activities have been accompanied by externally facing work taken up within EOSC and FAIR projects. In 2022 Members of the CESSDA Trust Working Group have established connections with a wider network of the Trust community through common interests or joint activities such as EOSC Nordic, SSHOC or FAIRsFAIR projects (see Figure 2).

EOSC Synchronisation and other trust and certification activities will continue through the ongoing FAIR IMPACT project.

CESSDA's certification support through the CoreTrustSeal in particular has been recognised as vital across the EOSC and globally.

Figure 2: CESSDA Trust Connections.

Mentorship & Widening

The rationale behind the Widening Working Group (WG) was to expand the CESSDA membership, provide capacity-building to new Service Providers and to maintain a network of non-member Service Providers (SPs).

Highlights in 2022

Third Wave of the CESSDA Mentorship Programme

The CESSDA mentorship programme offers **one-to-one support** between mature and new and less mature Service Providers or Service Providers which requested support on specific questions linked to data archives. The purpose of the programme is to help the mentees to define and realise their strategic, policy or technical short-term goals. During the period of 2021-2022 six mentees (three from CESSDA Service Providers (Iceland, Italy, and Slovakia) and three from partner countries (Bosnia and Herzegovina, Latvia, Lithuania) benefitted from the mentorship programme.

The **Ukraine National Data Bank of Sociological Data** joined the programme in 2022 based on an initiative carried out by the Czech Social Science Data Archive (CSDA). The CSDA supported the **Kyiv archive** during the war in Ukraine and saved the Ukrainian data for European researchers.

CESSDA Resource Directory

The CESSDA Resource Directory (RD) is a structured and documented collection of available documents, tools, and services for data archive professionals.¹⁶ The establishment of the Directory was a collaborative effort across CESSDA's membership.

Unlike search engines, the RD provides relevant and reliable resources that are directly related to social science research data archiving. Based on the expertise of CESSDA data archives, the RD offers specific resources designated for data archives and staff.

While the focus of the collection is on data archiving in social sciences, the RD is also open to adapting and extending its scope to cover new areas and interdisciplinary research. As of the end of 2022, the RD included over 600 resources organised into four categories based on the CoreTrustSeal requirements and the Open Archival Information System model: 1) Organisation, 2) Digital object management, 3) Communication and support, and 4) Technical infrastructure. In 2022, the focus was on adding information about data archiving tools provided by the CESSDA archives. The RD is publicly accessible via Zotero.

¹⁶ <https://www.cessda.eu/Tools/Resource-Directory>.

Training & Outreach

The task of the pillar Training is to disseminate CESSDA products and high quality social science research, raise the visibility of those products and train data users, data depositors and repository staff to leverage the full potential of those groups.

Users of CESSDA's tools and services encompass scholars from different SSH disciplines acting both as data producers and data users. Through training activities CESSDA engages with its stakeholders and raises awareness about the added value of its tools, services, and expertise and how CESSDA can support its members with their day-to-day research work.

Training for Researchers, Research Data Manager and Data Archive Experts

In 2022, 18 public events were held. The events targeted scientists, data archivists and other experts working in data repositories. For example, a workshop on the CESSDA Data Archiving Guide (DAG) was held at the IASSIST 2022 conference. Topics addressed questions such as how to manage and archive New Data Types (see chapter below), FAIR evaluation tools and services and various aspects of data management such as anonymisation for data sharing, Dataverse.

Other major data discovery activities took place: the **'International Data Discovery' events** comprising e.g. 'Ecological Consumption and Production', 'Tips and Tools for FAIR Sharing of Research Data'. **Local data discovery events** were held with topics on 'the Use of Secondary Data in Scientific Research in Serbia', 'Data Management in Social Sciences' in Macedonia, 'Surveyed or Registered' in Hungary, 'How to find data in the Danish National Archives' in Denmark', 'Research in Ethnic and Migration Studies' in Slovenia, to mention a few.

A total of 693 participants attended the events of which 53 percent were from the research community (see Figure 3). Materials for all events have been published in CESSDA's Zenodo community. Video recordings for most events (by agreement with the speakers) are available on CESSDA's Trainings YouTube channel and also on Zenodo.

Figure 3: Events per its main target audience (n=693). Source: Attendee report from events.

From seven events, on which registration data per country exists, we conclude that the largest participation was from the Netherlands, followed by Austria, Czech Republic, Croatia, Germany, Great Britain, Hungary, Ireland, Italy, Norway and Sweden (see Figure 4). 41 participants came from other parts of the world, among them the largest group was from the United States.

Figure 4: Attendees for seven events per country (n=334); Source: Attendee report from events.

The CESSDA Data Archiving Guide

The main work in 2022 was the preparation of two new additional chapters (chapters 5 and 6) in the CESSDA Data Archiving Guide (DAG). The fifth chapter deals with **‘FAIR-enabling and Trustworthy Qualities of Archives’**, in which the FAIR principles and the concept of trustworthiness are introduced. The sixth chapter **“Replication Services”** addresses issues related to the handling of replication materials in the social sciences, such as data, metadata, and code. The focus of this chapter is on the role of data repositories in supporting researchers and scholarly journals and publishers.

CESSDA Focus Activities

Focus Topic 'Journal Outreach'

Exchange of best practices between the data services of CESSDA members and SSH scientific journals is increasingly discussed in CESSDA. The working group on 'Journal Outreach' continued national pilot activities that were initiated in 2021. The goal of these activities was to provide support to journals in **developing data sharing policies** and to familiarise journal editors and authors with repositories where data linked to the articles can be stored, whether it pertains to specific data used in the particular paper (replication data) or is a complete dataset resulting from larger studies. The pilots were conducted in seven countries: Slovenia, Croatia, Greece, Switzerland, Finland, Sweden and Serbia.

A panel discussion on how CESSDA Data Archives joint efforts support journals in data sharing and reproducibility was held at the IASSIST conference 2022. Panel members presented the results of recent cooperation between selected CESSDA SPs and scientific journals.

The Journal and Data Archive Collaboration Forum was held in November 2022 as an online event. It brought together CESSDA SPs with SSH Journals. In addition to presenting the activities of the Journal Outreach group by SPs, publishers highlighted new initiatives and services related to linking data and scientific publications.

The Journal Outreach group also addressed data citation practices, which should be included in the instructions for authors and reviewers to enhance the **citability of the data**. Due to the significant importance of this topic, an informal group focused on data citation was recently established outside of the Journal Outreach group. This group aims to address the broader context of data citation.

Focus Topic 'Widening the Perimeter of Data'

In the context of the work on the topic 'Widening the Perimeter of Data' two surveys were undertaken in 2022: one with focus on the social sciences researchers **using social media data** and one addressed to CESSDA Service Providers to assess the archival holdings needed to store '**new data types**' (NDT). The surveys were combined with extensive desk research collecting material on NDT from previous CESSDA related projects. While NDT is a complex topic, there is a need to discuss those new data formats among the Service Providers to cater to increased demands from researchers.

Communications Activities

Social Media

Between January and December 2022, 662 tweets were posted to the CESSDA Twitter profile. Tweets about training activities showed above average performance. Tweets about the IASSIST conference and the CDC performed well as well as tweets promoting the CESSDA Data Catalogue were included based on the International Days proclaimed by the United Nations.

Content (encoded)	Freq.	Percent
1. CESSDA Data Catalogue	76	11.48
2. CESSDA Interviews	9	1.36
3. CESSDA Training events	153	23.11
4. DMEG	36	5.44
5. SP & CESSDA Partner job opportunities	58	8.76
6. SP Promotion	93	14.05
7. Tour of CESSDA news article	13	1.96
8. CESSDA Newsletter	17	2.57
9. Throwback Thursday	10	1.51
10. IASSIST	49	7.40
11. Not defined	148	22.36
Total	662	100.00

Figure 5: Number of tweets by content type. Source: CESSDA internal agenda report 21-22, 'Deliverable D34 Promotion on social media.

CESSDA Newsletter

A total of 11 issues of the CESSDA Newsletter were published in 2022. The content focused on conferences and events, training possibilities, publications, and other resources, as well as possibilities for funding and collaborations, vacancies, and news from the community. A new category was introduced to describe developments in CESSDA affiliated projects. From the rebranding in March 2021 to December 2022, the number of subscribers increased from 448 to 807. All issues of the newsletter are publicly available in the CESSDA Newsletter archive on the CESSDA website.

CESSDA's Involvement in EC Projects

At the core of CESSDA lies a steadfast commitment to collaboration and progress within the European research landscape. Over the years, the CESSDA Consortium has been a dedicated contributor to several vital projects, each playing a crucial role in supporting the European Commission's commitment to fostering innovation and partnership.

In 2022, this journey continued for CESSDA through its participation in 10 projects, assuming support and coordination roles. These projects contribute to CESSDA's framework for involvement in the European Research Area (ERA). They have three major goals: 1. Supporting the Europe-wide building of the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) 2. Joining relevant research data communities in their initiatives to work with social science data and data archiving, and 3. Helping to build a stronger and healthier Research Infrastructure Landscape.

Figure 6: CESSDA's framework of involvement in the European Research Area (ERA) via EC projects.

CESSDA Supporting the Building of the EOSC

The Social Sciences and Humanities Open Cloud

CESSDA contributed to and benefited from the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) as a unified, open-access research environment that fosters seamless data sharing and collaboration.

Financed under INFRAEOSC 04-2018 as one out of five cluster projects, the Social Sciences and Humanities Open Cloud (SSHOC) cluster project prepared for the seamless connection of the cluster to the EOSC.¹⁷

The project coordinated by CESSDA ensured that Tools and Services from CESSDA and other research infrastructures in the SSH domain were technologically aligned and integrated into the SSH Open Marketplace, and subsequently onboarded into the EOSC. CESSDA organised training and awareness-raising events on its tools and services developed within the project, contributed to the development of the SSH Training discovery toolkit, and fostered the Training community. These efforts solidified CESSDA as a training facilitator in the fields of social sciences and data archiving (see chapter on training). CESSDA's experience in CoreTrustSeal (CTS) certification supported 13 different institutions with data repositories to achieve CTS.

The project closed with a SSHOC Final Conference, titled *'Advancing SSH Research with SSHOCingly good and sustainable resources'* in April 2022. The event gathered 290 participants from Europe and beyond. The SSHOC project provided a template for a sustainable model of collaboration to ensure that the SSH community is an important player in the ERA and Open Science initiatives.

Apart from the CESSDA Main Office, nine Service Providers (Sikt, UK Data Service, UL-ADP, GESIS, SND, TAU-FSD, FORS, AUSSDA and DNA) ensured that CESSDA as a Consortium contributed to all nine Work Packages.

Figure 7: SSHOC Project final conference in Brussels attracted 290 participants.

¹⁷ <https://www.sshopencloud.eu/>

CESSDA and FAIR

CESSDA joined the project Consortium FAIR-IMPACT (**Expanding FAIR Solutions across EOSC**) together with Sikt and UK Data Service to support the implementation of the FAIR principles.¹⁸ Realising a FAIR EOSC by expanding FAIR solutions across the EOSC, this project has aimed to identify practices, policies, tools and technical specifications to guide researchers, repository managers, research performing organisations, policy makers and citizen scientists towards a FAIR data management cycle.

The focus of the consortium is on **persistent identifiers (PIDs), metadata, ontologies, metrics, certification and interoperability**, starting with real-life use cases from the social sciences and humanities, and other science disciplines. In 2022 FAIR-IMPACT has set up its coordinating mechanisms and focused on the preparatory work for a system of cascading grants and an open call for the *EOSC FAIR Champions*.

Figure 8: CESSDA and partners in the FAIR-IMPACT project use cases (Credit: FAIR-IMPACT).¹⁹

EOSC Future Project

Technical Implementation

Since the aim of the EOSC is to provide a single sign-on system, access to interoperable resources and support to manage the full lifecycle of its data, CESSDA with expertise in research data management joined the EOSC Future project.²⁰ CESSDA partners conduct training events on EOSC, develop training materials and courses, and support the EOSC Training catalogue - Knowledge Hub. CESSDA's instrumental role in **software quality** is reflected through the leadership of the working group on Software Quality Assurance, which provides guidelines for EOSC software developers. CESSDA also leads the work package responsible for the design and development of the Portal Demand Layer (i.e. components for end users, such as the Marketplace). In addition, CESSDA contributes to the integration of the Community Services and Products into EOSC.

¹⁸ <https://fair-impact.eu/>.

¹⁹ <https://fair-impact.eu/fair-impact-expanding-fair-solutions-across-eosc>.

²⁰ <https://eoscfuture.eu/>.

CESSDA's Support to the EOSC Steering Board

CESSDA also played a crucial role in the project by engaging and collaborating with EU Member States and Associated Countries. CESSDA MO was a vital part of the supporting team of the **EOSC Steering Board Subgroup on Monitoring**. The activity aimed to map the readiness levels of different countries towards EOSC, enhancing the profile of EOSC and the EOSC Observatory.²¹

The CESSDA team conducted surveys among the members of the EOSC Steering Board and authored two reports that focused on the financial investments dimension, specifically providing suggestions for calculating the national contribution to EOSC.²²

With the Main Office and eight CESSDA archives (UL-ADP, UK Data Service, ISSDA, EKKE, TAU-FSD, FORS, SND and AUSSDA) CESSDA contributed to the project aims to further develop the EOSC Portal, EOSC-Core and EOSC-Exchange of the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC).

Figure 9: Two reports authored by the CESSDA team in EOSC Future.

TRIPLE

CESSDA together with a team of three national expert teams from UK Data Service, UL-ADP, and TAU-FSD has been part of a three-year project at the crossroads of building EOSC tools and supporting the research communities. CESSDA partners made significant contributions to the project **TRIPLE (Transforming Research through Innovative Practices for Linked Interdisciplinary Exploration)**.²³ Notably, UK Data Service and FSD participated in service development including the multilingual GoTriple Vocabulary and metadata schema, and linking concepts (i.e. a knowledge organisation system) with the CESSDA ELSST thesaurus.²⁴

An outstanding achievement was the inclusion of CESSDA Data Catalogue metadata in GoTriple, ensuring broad discoverability for researchers. CESSDA played a key role in defining interoperability requirements for the

21 EOSC Observatory: <https://eoscobservatory.eosc-portal.eu/home>.

22 Reports are available in Zenodo: Vanja Komljenović, & Irena Vipavc Brvar. (2022). Analysis of Survey on National Contributions to EOSC 2021 (Version V1). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7410828>; Vanja Komljenović, Gareth O'Neill, Martina Draščić Capar, & Istvan Karasz. (2023). Calculating National Financial Contributions to EOSC (Version V1). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7951324>.

23 <https://project.gotriple.eu/>.

24 <https://elsst.cessda.eu/concept-scheme>.

GoTriple minimum viable prototype, aligning them carefully with EOSC and SSHOC Marketplaces. Additionally, CESSDA's UL-ADP team contributed to diverse outreach events such as training, conferences, hackathons and impromptu ThatCamps, fostering vibrant exchanges of experiences and ideas. As the TRIPLE project will reach its conclusion in early 2023, CESSDA's impact will continue to resonate through a Memorandum of Understanding signed by OPERAS and CESSDA (see chapter MoU between CESSDA and OPERAS).

CESSDA and the Research Data Communities

CESSDA caters to a large research community, consisting of scholars from different disciplines who serve both as data producers and data users. These communities come from different social sciences thematic domains. CESSDA actively engages with these research communities to enhance their awareness of the invaluable possibilities offered by its tools, services, and expertise. CESSDA endeavours to showcase how it can effectively support and empower research communities in their day-to-day research endeavours, and thus joins EC projects with that purpose.

COORDINATE

CESSDA worked in the project COORDINATE and collaborated with the data survey community on **child and youth well-being** (EuroCohort - Growing Up in Digital Europe) to make the data more findable, accessible, interoperable and reusable.²⁵ In 2022, the COORDINATE Virtual Access Portal's architectural diagram was finalised. All the survey data will be deposited in the CESSDA data archive for long-term preservation. The CESSDA team has also been leading the work on a data platform for virtual collections modelled after the CESSDA Data Catalogue and the CESSDA metadata harvesting system. The metadata guidelines were finalised in 2022. The work was done by CESSDA's Service Providers FSD and CROSSDA. The Service Provider ADP provided training courses on the use of secondary data from research infrastructures and on data management planning, covering statistics courses, Data Management Plan courses, summer schools or training courses for non-scientific stakeholders.

HumMingBird

CESSDA has collaborated with the research community on **data on migration** via the HumMingBird project (With Service Providers SoDaNet-EKKE and IEN).²⁶ In 2022 CESSDA's team wrote a chapter on 'CESSDA Data Catalogue: opportunities and challenges to explore mobility and migration' in the collective volume *Data Science for Migration and Mobility*, published by Oxford University Press.²⁷ A significant dataset was stored in the thematic database *Research Data on Migration and the refugee crisis* in the SoDaNet-EKKE. IEN led the fieldwork and report preparation on conducting expert interviews with all relevant stakeholders and interest groups in the field of migration in Serbia.

²⁵ <https://www.coordinate-network.eu/>.

²⁶ <https://hummingbird-h2020.eu/>.

²⁷ Salah, A.A., Korkmaz, E.E., & Bircan, T. (eds.) (2022), *Data Science for Migration and Mobility*, Proc. British Academy, Oxford University Press; Available online: <https://global.oup.com/academic/product/data-science-for-migration-and-mobility-9780197267103?view=Grid&lang=en&cc=lb>.

BY-COVID

Realising the value of social sciences data for **public health**, CESSDA has joined the interdisciplinary initiative BY-COVID.²⁸ The project provides comprehensive **open data on SARS-CoV-2** and other **infectious diseases** across medical sciences and public health, social sciences and policies. Since 2022 the COVID-19 Data Portal includes a section on social sciences and humanities data. About 500+ COVID-19-related studies are from the CESSDA Data Catalogue. CESSDA data was the first resource available in the BY-COVID portal. The onboarding was a result of collaboration between FSD, DANS and EKKE as CESSDA partners. The onboarding process followed an iterative process parallel with the development of the portal.

eRImote

Another interdisciplinary initiative CESSDA joined in 2022 is the eRImote project.²⁹ This is a one-of-a-kind initiative that considers **solutions for digital and remote service provision** across all research domains to improve the accessibility and resilience of European research infrastructures. eRImote will also explore new solutions and define use cases to develop and test their implementation in different research infrastructure settings. CESSDA's collaborative efforts involving CESSDA's Main Office and the Service Providers FORS and UK Data Service, will play a pivotal role in contributing to a Green Paper. In 2022, two workshops took place: one focusing on remote training for researchers and staff from research infrastructures, and one on data access security and quality management of remote operations.

CESSDA's Support to the Research Infrastructure Landscape

In 2022, CESSDA contributed to the European research infrastructure landscape through three projects: One on strengthening the collaboration between the ERICs institutions in Europe, one on developing training tailored for research infrastructures staff, and one supporting an ESFRI project to build and formulate a research infrastructure for collecting gender and generations data.

ERIC Forum Implementation Project

The ERIC Forum Implementation Project ended in 2022.³⁰ Since its set-up in 2019, the Forum has produced several policy briefs (e.g. on funding models for access to research infrastructures), and position papers (e.g. Key Performance Indicators, Horizon Europe Missions, EOSC and more). The ERIC Forum project also served as a foundation for the development of relevant guidance documents, training and best practices that would support ERICs in the preparatory phase, and once established.

²⁸ <https://by-covid.org/>.

²⁹ <https://erimote.eu/home>.

³⁰ <https://www.eric-forum.eu/>.

RITrainPlus

The RITrainPlus project aims at creating a training program for current and **future managers of research infrastructures** and core facilities.³¹ CESSDA's representatives in the project are FORS, UL-ADP, and AUSSDA. In 2022, AUSSDA conducted a study to identify competencies and skills. It also established specialised **post-doctoral courses to enhance managerial capabilities** of staff. For scalability, an instructional design methodology and coaching program were devised. A community of practice led by UL-ADP was tailored for research infrastructure and core facility managers. Other activities comprised:

- A webinar "Starting a new post in a research infrastructure" organised by the Main Office.
- A workshop on "Strengthening Managerial Capacities in Data Policy Management" organised by FORS.
- A staff visit event hosted by UL-ADP introducing complex work in Research Infrastructures to the team from Bosnia and Herzegovina.

The image shows a Zoom webinar interface. The main content area has a dark blue background with white and yellow text. At the top left, it says "First CoP webinar" and "RITrainPlus" with a logo. The title is "Starting a new post in a research infrastructure" in large yellow font. Below the title, it says "13 May 2022 • 12:00 - 13:30 CET". Under "Speakers:", there is a list of four names and their titles. At the bottom, there is a URL: "https://bit.ly/ritrainplus". On the right side, there is a video thumbnail of a woman with glasses, labeled "bonniehoff-b...". In the bottom right corner, there is a Zoom logo and a video thumbnail of a woman wearing a headset.

First CoP webinar

RITrain^{PLUS}

"Starting a new post in a research infrastructure"

13 May 2022 • 12:00 - 13:30 CET

Speakers:

- Meredith Goins, Executive Director of the World Data System - IPO,
- Bonnie Wolff-Boenisch, Director of the Consortium of European Social Science Data Archives (CESSDA),
- Darja Fišer, future Director of 'Common Language Resources and Technology Infrastructure (CLARIN ERIC),
- Ari Asmi, Director of RDA Europe.

<https://bit.ly/ritrainplus>

bonniehoff-b...

zoom

GGP-5D

In 2022, CESSDA joined the GGP-5D project supporting the Generations and Gender Programme (GGP) working towards its establishment as a permanent research infrastructure with its own legal entity.³² The GGP is a unique interdisciplinary research infrastructure focused on **population and family dynamics**, collecting and disseminating cross-nationally comparable longitudinal data. It addresses crucial scientific and societal challenges related to the causes and consequences of demographic changes.

³¹ <https://ritrainplus.eu/>.

³² <https://www.ggp-i.org/ggp-5d/>.

Towards New Initiatives in Horizon Europe

CESSDA was solicited to join several EC project proposals due to its past engagement and successful cross-disciplinary collaborations. By the end of 2022 CESSDA joined eight project proposals to be submitted in early 2023:

- **ERIC Forum project continuation**
- **Infra4NextGen** (Providing research infrastructure services to support Next Generation EU)
- **O.S.C.A.R.S.** (Open Science Clusters' Action for Research and Society)
- **OStrails** (Open Science Plan-Track-Assess Pathways)
- **EOSC Beyond** (EOSC Beyond: advancing innovation and collaboration for research), **OSC-ENTRUST** (A European Network of TRUSTed research environments)
- **EOSC - Q** (Leveraging Synergies across Research Communities for Quality Software and Services in EOSC), and
- **QUANTUM** (Quality, Utility and Maturity Measured; Developing a Data Quality and Utility Label for HealthData@EU).

Figure 10: Cross-discipline initiatives: Open Science stakeholders and Science Cluster representatives in 2022.

Financial Statements 2022

Income Statement (EUR)

Operating income and expenses	Note	2022	2021
Operating income	1	1 882 678	1 600 557
Total operating income		1 882 678	1 600 557
Operating expenses			
Payroll expense	2	860 690	1 060 661
Depreciation of fixed assets	3	0	1 648
Other operating expenses		582 643	988 132
Total operating expenses		1 443 333	2 050 441
Operating profit/loss		439 344	-449 884
Financial income and expenses			
Other interest income		394	-1 261
Other financial income		8 280	13 492
Other interest expenses		9 080	4 606
Other financial expenses		2 723	-4 261
Net financial income and expenses		-3 130	11 886
Annual net result		436 215	-437 998
From/to other equity		0	437 998
Net brought forward		436 215	-437 998

Balance Statement (EUR)

Assets	Note	2022	2021
Current assets			
Receivables			
Accounts receivables		26 216	30 000
Other short-term receivables	5	491 366	307 155
Total receivables		517 582	337 155
Bank deposits, cash and cash equivalents			
Bank deposits, cash and cash equivalents	4	1 350 038	1 352 664
Total bank deposits, cash and cash equivalents		1 350 038	1 352 664

Assets	Note	2022	2021
Total current assets		1 867 619	1 689 818
Total assets		1 867 619	1 689 818

Balance Statement (EUR)

Equity and liabilities	Note	2022	2021
Equity			
Other equity		605 099	169 067
Total retained earnings		605 099	169 067

Total equity		605 099	169 067
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Liabilities			
Current liabilities			
Trade payables		61 600	92 038
Public duties payable		63 204	45 054
Other current liabilities	5	1 137 716	1 383 658
Total current liabilities		1 262 520	1 520 750

Total liabilities		1 262 520	1 520 750
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Total equity and liabilities		1 867 619	1 689 818
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Accounting Principles

The annual accounts have been prepared in conformity with the Accounting Act and NRS 8 - Good accounting practice for small companies.

Foreign Currency

Monetary foreign currency items are valued at the exchange rate on the balance sheet date.

Operating Revenues and Expenses

Revenues consist mainly of grants and project revenues. Received payments related to activities not carried out at year-end are recognised in the balance sheet as unearned income and classified as other short-term debt.

Expenses are recognised in accordance with the matching principle. This means that expenses are recognised in the same period as the related income.

Revenues from EC projects are recognised according to submitted financial reports approved by EC or other direct cost which will be covered by pre-financing from EC.

Tax

CESSDA ERIC is a non-profit organisation and is not liable for corporation tax in accordance with the Tax Law § 2-32.

Classification and Valuation of Fixed Assets

Fixed assets include assets included for long-term ownership and use. Fixed assets are valued at acquisition cost. Property, plant and equipment are entered in the balance sheet and depreciated over the asset's economic lifetime. The depreciation period for real property acquired after 2009 is divided into the part that represents the building and the part that represents fixed technical installations. Property, plant and equipment are written down to a recoverable amount in the case of fall in value which is expected not to be temporary. The recoverable amount is the higher of the net sale value and value in use. Value in use is the present value of future cash flows related to the asset. Write-downs are reversed when the basis for the write-down is no longer present.

Classification and Valuation of Current Assets

Current assets and short-term liabilities normally include items that fall due for payment within one year of the balance sheet date, as well as items that relate to the stock cycle. Current assets are valued at the lower of acquisition cost and fair value.

Receivables

Receivables from customers and other receivables are entered at par value after deducting a provision for expected losses. The provision for losses is made on the basis of an individual assessment of the respective receivables.

Pension

The Norwegian branch has established a defined benefit pension scheme. The pension premium is classified as a payroll expense.

NOTES

Note 1 - Revenues

Breakdown of income	2022	2021
Members' contributions	1 882 678	1 557 182
Other Grant income	0	40 881
Other	0	2 495
Total	1 882 678	1 600 557

Pre-fundings received by the EC and which relate to the following year(s) have been excluded from the income and treated as deferred income, classified as other short-term liabilities.

Note 2 - Salary Costs and Number of Man-Years

Salary costs	2022	2021
Salaries*	643 866	876 478
Employment tax	113 519	102 800
Pension costs	81 297	59 239
Other benefits	22 008	22 145
Total	860 690	1 060 661

*In 2021 hired labour of EUR 117 418, was classified as salary. In 2022, hired labour of EUR 29 510 is classified as other expenses.

In 2022 the company employed 10 man-years.

Note 3 - Tangible Assets

Assets	Equipment and other movables	Total
Acquisition costs 01.01.2022	67 808	67 808
Acquisition costs 31.12.2022	67 808	67 808
Accumulated depreciations 31.12	67 808	67 808
Book value 31.12.2022	0	0
Acc. depreciations and write-downs 01.01.2022	67 808	67 808
Acc. depreciations and write-downs 31.12.2022	67 808	67 808
Economic lifetime	3 - 5 years	
Depreciation plan	Linear	

Note 4 - Bank Deposits

Bank deposits	2022	2021
Restricted cash-employee tax deduction funds	29 959	25 989
Restricted cash-deposit funds	34 502	34 470
Bank deposits in NOK	60 710	10 584
Bank deposits in EUR	1 224 866	1 281 620
Total bank deposits	1 350 038	1 352 664

CESSDA ERIC has a currency risk associated with the exchange rate developments. Allocated funding to projects is paid in Euro. The bank deposits are in Norwegian Kroner and Euro.

Note 5 - EC Projects

EC Projects	2022	2021
EC projects; pre-financing, received as at 31.12	-988 831	-1 226 747
EC projects; accrued costs as at 31.12	475 660	274 615
Net EC projects	-513 172	-952 132

Pre-financing of EC projects is classified as deferred income.

Costs related to deferred income are classified as other short-term receivables.

Annex 1: CESSDA ERIC Members, Observers and Service Providers in December 2022

Country	Representing entity	Service Provider	GA Delegates	SPF Delegates
Austria	Federal Ministry of Education, Science and Research (BMBWF)	AUSSDA - The Austrian Social Science Data Archive	Matthias Reiter-Pázmándy, BMBWF Bettina Glaser, BMBWF (deputy) Lars Kaczmirek, (AUSSDA) Lisa Hönegger (AUSSDA) from 01.02.22 until 31.07.22	Lars Kaczmirek Lisa Hönegger from 01.02.22 until 31.07.22
Belgium	BELSPO - Belgian Scientific Policy Office	SOHDA - Social Sciences and Humanities Data Archive	Aziz Naji (BELSPO)	Benjamin Peuch Laura Van Den Borre
Croatia	Ministry of Science and Education	CROSSDA - Croatian Social Science Data Archive	Jelena Ilic Dreven, Staša Skenžić, (Ministry of Science and Education)	Marijana Glavica
Czech Republic	Ministry of Education, Youth and Sports	CSDA - Czech Social Science Data Archive	Nad'a Vaverova, (Ministry of Education and Sport) Jindrich Krejci (CSDA)	Jindrich Krejci Yana Leontiyeva
Denmark	Danish Agency for Science and Higher Education	DNA - Danish Data	Kirsten Villadsen Kristmar (DNA)	Jan Dalsten Sørensen
Finland	Academy of Finland	FSD - Finnish Social Science Data Archive	Jussi Varkemaa Academy of Finland (until 31.08.22) Vilma Lehtinen, Academy of Finland (from 31.08.22)	Mari Kleemola, FSD Helena Laaksonen

Country	Representing entity	Service Provider	GA Delegates	SPF Delegates
France	Ministry of Education, Higher Education and Research	PROGEDO/CNRS	Fabrice Boudjaaba, CNRS Basudeb Chaudhuri (until 28.10.22), Ministry Education, Higher Education and Research Johanna Etner (from November 2022) Ministry of Education, Higher Education and Research	Sebastien Oliveau
Germany	Federal Ministry of Education and Research (BMBF)	GESIS - Leibniz Institute for the Social Sciences	Miriam Schriefers, (DLR Project Management Agency) Alexia Katsanidou, (GESIS)	Libby Bishop
Greece	Greek research infrastructure for the social sciences	So.Da.Net	John Kallas Dimitra Kondyli	Dimitra Kondyli
Hungary	The National Research, Development and Innovation Office (NRDI Office - NKFIH)	TÁRKI Foundation	Orsolya Rigó-Ditzendy (until 01.08.22), NKFIH Péter Aranyi (from 01.08.22), NKFIH Péter Hegedűs, (TARKI)	Peter Hegedus
Iceland	Ministry of Education, Science and Culture of Iceland	DATICE - Social Science Research Institute	Guðbjörg Andrea Jónsdóttir (DATICE)	Örnólfur Thorlacius Guðbjörg Andrea Jónsdóttir
Ireland	Irish Research Council	ISSDA - Irish Social Science Data Archive	Peter Brown (until 03.10.22), Research Council Rosemary Sweeney (from 03.10.22), Research Council	John Howard Julia Barrett

Country	Representing entity	Service Provider	GA Delegates	SPF Delegates
Italy	Ministry of Universities and Research; entity - Consiglio nazionale delle Ricerche (CNR)	DASSI - Data Archive Social Sciences Italy	Andrea Filippetti (until 22.02.22), CNR Mario Paolucci (from 22.02.22), CNR Grazia Pavoncello (until 22.11.22), CNR Saverio Foti (from 22.11.22), CNR	Sonia Stefanizzi
Netherlands	The Netherlands Organisation for Scientific Research (NWO)	DANS - Data Archiving and Networked Services	Joris Voskuilen, (NWO) Ingrid Dillo (DANS)	Ricarda Braukmann Ingrid Dillo
North Macedonia	Ministry of Education and Science	Ss. Cyril and Methodius University in Skopje	Klime Babunski, Ss. Cyril and Methodius University Elvan Hasanovic (both until 10.08.22), Ministry Education and Science Borco Aleksov (from 10.08.22), Ministry Education and Science	Aneta Cekikj
Norway	Research Council of Norway (RCN)	Sikt - Norwegian Agency for Shared Services in Education and Research	Siri Lader Bruhn (RCN), Vigdis Kvalheim, (Sikt)	Vigdis Kvalheim Ingvild Eide Graff (until 01.04.22) Bodil Agasøster (from 01.04.22)
Portugal	Institute of Social Science, University of Lisbon	APIS - Portuguese Archive of Social Information	Pedro Moura Ferreira, APIS Jose Manuel Mendes, Centre for Social Studies	Jose Manuel Mendes Pedro Moura Ferreira
Serbia	Ministry of Education, Science and Technological Development (MPN)	DCS - Data Centre Serbia for Social Sciences	Aleksandra Bradic-Martinovic, (DCS) Marija Velickovic, MPN	Aleksandra Bradic-Martinovic

Country	Representing entity	Service Provider	GA Delegates	SPF Delegates
Slovakia	Ministry of Education, Science, Research and Sport of the Slovak Republic	SASD - Slovak Archive of Social Data	Miloslav Bahna, Institute for Sociology of Slovak Academy of Sciences	Miloslav Bahna Katarina Strapcova
Slovenia	Ministry of Education, Science and Sport (MIZs)	ADP - Social Science Data Archives	Albin Kralj, MIZs Janez Stebe, ADP	Janez Stebe Irena Vipavc Brvar
Sweden	Swedish Research Council (SRC)	SND - Swedish National Data Service	Susanna Bylin, (SRC) Kenneth Nelson, Stockholm University	Iris Alfredsson Max Petzold
Switzerland	FORS – the Swiss Centre of Expertise in the Social Sciences	FORS	Georg Lutz (FORS) Brian Kleiner (FORS Katharina Eggenberger (SERI))	Brian Kleiner Alexandra Stam
United Kingdom	BEIS - Department for Business, Energy & Industrial Strategy	UK Data Service	Carlos Pueyo (until 15.02.22), ESRC UKRI Richard Welpton (from 15.02.22), ESRC UKRI Matthew Woollard, UK Data Service, Darren Bell, UK Data Service (from 05.07.22)	Herve L'Hours Matthew Woollard Darren Bell from June 2022

